

The Photochemical Reduction of Ferric Salts by Mandelic, Lactic and Tartaric Acids.

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It is well known that many organic substances reduce ferric salts in presence of light. A large amount of work has already been done on the photochemical oxidation of oxalic acid by ferric salts. But quantitative work on the oxidation of other acids by ferric salts is lacking in thoroughness and accuracy. Reference should be made to the work of Benrath (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, **74**, 115) Winther and Oxolt-Howe (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1914, **14**, 196.) and Bölin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, **87**, 490). They all found that the dark reaction had negligible velocity and that the photochemical reactions were zeromolecular. Benrath found that in the case of oxidation of tartaric acid the speed of oxidation is also independent of the concentration of tartaric acid. He did not, however, investigate this point in the case of other acids. This observation of Benrath appears to be inconsistent with a large number of investigations carried out in this laboratory, according to which the inverse of the speed of reaction plotted against the inverse of the concentration of acceptor molecules gave a straight line, $\frac{d(1/\text{speed})}{d(1/\text{conc.})}$ having always a positive value. A systematic investigation of these reactions was therefore carried out with a view to elucidating the inner mechanism of the process of photochemical oxidation.

It should be noted at the outset that while the oxidation of lactic and mandelic acids consists in the splitting off of carbon dioxide and oxidation of two hydrogen atoms to give respectively acetaldehyde and benzaldehyde, the corresponding oxidation of tartaric acid is a very complicated process. We obtain a host of substances as the reaction products *e.g.*, carbon dioxide, formaldehyde, glyoxal, glyoxalic acid, etc. Some of these reaction products are capable of still further oxidation by ferric salt. Hence the results of experiments on photochemical oxidation of tartaric acid are expected to be different from those observed with lactic and mandelic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The source of light was a 1000 c.p. Pointolite lamp: the strength of current and voltage were maintained constant by means of a regulating resistance. A parallel beam of light was obtained by placing a convex lens at its focal distance from the lamp. The intensity of light was varied by using lenses of different focal lengths. Different spectral regions were isolated by the use of following filters.

Filter A consisted of solutions of Crystal violet and copper sulphate and transmitted a narrow region of spectrum about $448\mu\mu$.

Filter B consisted of solutions of "Doppel grün" and copper sulphate and transmitted a narrow region of spectrum about $448\mu\mu$.

Filter C consisted of a plate of Corning glass which transmitted a spectral region between $350\mu\mu$ and $420\mu\mu$. Since glass reaction vessels were used the effective radiations had wave-lengths lying between $360\mu\mu$ and $420\mu\mu$.

With these filters therefore, small regions of the spectrum round $488\mu\mu$, $448\mu\mu$ and $400\mu\mu$ could be isolated and their photochemical efficiencies studied. The intensity of radiation absorbed was measured by means of a Moll thermopile and Moll galvanometer and compared with the intensity of a standard Hefner. The actual procedure consisted in observing first, the deflections of the galvanometer when light fell on the thermopile after passing through the reacting mixture in the reaction cell, and then observing the deflection when the reaction cell was filled with water only. The difference in deflections is a measure of the light absorbed.

The rectangular reaction cell made of plane parallel glass plates was placed inside a double-jacketted box provided with a glass window to admit light from the lamp. The box was maintained at a constant temperature by circulating water through its annular space from a thermostat by means of a pump. Solutions of ferric salt and organic acids were separately allowed to take up the temperature of the thermostat and were then mixed inside the reaction cell. The rate of reduction of ferric salt was measured by titration. It is essential for accurate work that no extraneous source of light should enter the reaction cell, and the reaction was carried in a perfectly dark room, the only light entering the reaction cell being that obtained from the Pointolite lamp through the glass window.

*Effect of Complete Absorption of incident Rays by thin Layers of
 Reacting Mixture close to Surface of Incidence on Titration Value :
 The Need of Shaking the Reaction Cell before each Titration.*

In the experimental arrangement described before, the reaction cell was kept fixed inside a box and the reacting mixture was pipetted out at intervals and titrated, with minimum disturbance of the reaction cell. The results obtained specially when illumination was effected by spectral regions round $448\mu\mu$ and $400\mu\mu$ were irregular and disquieting. Table I will bring out the nature of these irregularities.

TABLE I.

Composition of reacting mixture—Mandelic acid= $0\cdot1$ M.
 Hydrochloric acid= $0\cdot05$ M.
 Ferric chloride= $0\cdot025$ M.

Spectral region—about $448\mu\mu$.

Time in hours.	Titre values : C.c. of $N/500$ -thiosulphate for 2 c.c. of reacting mixture.	Diff. between titration values.
0	25.2	1.6 (between 0 and 1)
1	23.6	2.2 (between 1 and 2)
2	20.4	3.05 (between 2 and 3)
3	18.85	

It appeared as if there was an auto-acceleration. Careful investigation however showed that this irregularity is due to the photochemical reaction taking place in a thin layer close to the surface on which light was incident, and to the slowness of the process of diffusion resulting in the solution being inhomogeneous as regards concentration of ferric chloride. This disturbing influence was found to be much smaller for light round spectral region $488\mu\mu$, but very much greater for light round spectral region $400\mu\mu$.

The explanation is obvious. The absorption of light by ferric chloride solutions increases very rapidly as the wave-length diminishes for larger wave-lengths, *e.g.*, $488\mu\mu$, the reaction almost takes place in the whole bulk of the liquid mixture, though of course, the speed of reaction in the layers close to the surface of incident light is much larger than in the distant layers. The resulting inhomogeneity

of the mixture as regards ferric salt concentration is not therefore very great. But for wave-lengths round $400\mu\mu$ a very thin layer of the reacting mixture close to surface of incidence completely absorbs the radiation, and the photochemical reaction is confined within this layer. Since the process of diffusion is slow, the resulting inhomogeneity is very considerable. The titration values recorded in Table II were obtained with this precaution that the reacting mixture was vigorously shaken before each pipetting off.

TABLE II.

Intensity and quality of light, and composition of reacting mixture same as in Table I.

Time in hours.	N/500-Thiosulphate for 2 c.c. solution.	Difference.
0	25.2 c.c.	2.3 (between 0 and 1)
1	22.9	2.35 (between 1 and 2)
2	20.55	2.35 (between 2 and 3)

It will be seen that with this precaution, the reaction is found to be zero-molecular, provided the concentration of the oxidisable acid molecule does not undergo considerable variation in the course of experiment. That the above explanation of the irregularity noticed in Table I was correct was further confirmed in the following way. The reaction cell was nearly completely filled with reacting mixture and exposed to light for a definite interval. The cell was withdrawn from the constant temperature box, the contents thoroughly shaken and the amount of total reaction was estimated. The cell was washed, dried, filled up to the same extent with the same reacting mixture, exposed for a longer interval, and the amount of total reaction again determined. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE IIIA.

Composition of reacting mixture—Mandelic acid = 0.5 M.
 Ferric chloride = 0.025 M.
 Hydrochloric acid = 0.05 M.
 Spectral region—about $390\mu\mu$. Reaction cell = $2.5 \times 2.3 \times 0.5$ cm.

	Total change in terms of <i>N</i> /500-thiosulphate.			
Exposed for 1 hour	3.4 c.c.
Exposed for 2 hours	6.4 c.c.
Exposed for 3 hours	10.8 c.c.

TABLE IIIB.

Experimental conditions were same as in Table IIIA except that 0.5 *M*-mandelic acid was substituted by 0.5*M*-tartaric acid.

	Total change in terms of <i>N</i> /500-thiosulphate.			
Exposed for 2 hours	1.85 c.c.
Exposed for 4 hours	3.8 c.c.

TABLE IIIC.

Experimental conditions same as in Table IIIA except that a new reaction cell 3 × 3 × 1 cm. was used.

	Total change in terms of <i>N</i> /500-thiosulphate.			
Exposed for 1½ hours	8 c.c.
Exposed for 4½ hours	23.8 c.c.

It is quite clear from the above tables, that *with excess of tartaric acid or mandelic acid as acceptor* the photochemical reduction of ferric chloride is zeromolecular even with light of wave-length of about 390μ. A comparison of data in Table IIIA and IIIC will at once bring out the fact that the amount of ferrous salt produced per hour is proportional to the area of the surface on which light was incident.

Depth of Reaction Cell necessary for complete Absorption of Radiations of different Wave-lengths.

Our reactions were carried out mostly with a ferric chloride solution whose concentration was 0.025 *M*. A relationship between the speed of the zeromolecular reaction and the intensity of incident radiation can only be expected to exist only when the whole of the incident radiation is absorbed by the reacting mixture in the cell. For ascertaining the depth of layer necessary for complete absorption of light, rectangular cells, having the same surface area but different depths were used. If the absorption of light were always complete, we would expect that the titre for 2 c.c. of the reaction mixture after exposure for one hour should be inversely as the thicknesses of the cells. The results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Ferric chloride = 0.025N.		Hydrochloric acid = 0.05N _z	
Conc. of mandelic acid.	x/t (1 cm. thick cell)	x/t (1.5 cm. thick cell.)	Ratio of velocities.
Spectral region = 488 $\mu\mu$			
0.5 M	3.1	2.35	1.31
0.05 M	2.5	1.95	1.23
0.025 M	2.1	1.64	1.28
Spectral region = 448 $\mu\mu$			
0.5 M	2.57	1.85	1.38
0.2 M	2.45	1.78	1.38
0.1 M	2.33	1.68	1.39
Spectral region = 390 $\mu\mu$			
0.5 M	1.2	0.82	1.48

It is clear from the above tables, that a thickness of 0.5 cm. is sufficient for complete absorption of light in region 390 $\mu\mu$ by a 0.025N-ferric chloride solution, whereas for wave-lengths between 478 $\mu\mu$ and 410 $\mu\mu$ for complete absorption a thickness of 1 cm. is not sufficient but a thickness of 1.5 cm. is necessary. In the case of light of wave-lengths between 526 $\mu\mu$ and 454 $\mu\mu$ a thickness of 1.5 cm. is not even sufficient for complete absorption, and for this region it is always essential to measure the intensity of radiation absorbed by actual experiment.

Effect of Hydrochloric Acid on the Speed of Reaction.

It is necessary to add a certain amount of hydrochloric acid to a solution of ferric chloride in order to prevent the hydrolysis of ferric chloride solutions. The effect of adding varying quantities of hydrochloric acid to the reacting mixtures under different conditions of experiment is shown in Table V.

TABLE V.

Spectral region = 488 $\mu\mu$.	
Ferric chloride = 0.025M.	Mandelic acid = 0.1M.
Hydrochloric acid = 0.0125 M.	

Time in hours.	($a-x$).	x/t ($N/500$ -thiosulphate for 2 c.c. of the mixture).
0	25.2	—
1	22.1	3.1 c.c.
2	18.95	3.15
3	15.8	3.15

TABLE VI.

Hydrochloric acid=0.05M.

Time in hours.	($a-x$).	x/t ($N/500$ -thiosulphate for 2 c.c. of the mixture).
0	25.2	—
1	22.4	2.8 c.c.
2	19.55	2.8
3	16.8	2.75

For 448μ the values of x/t with 0.0125M-hydrochloric acid were found to be 2.4 and 2.35 respectively.

Hydrochloric acid lowers the extinction coefficient of ferric chloride; necessarily the velocity diminishes as the concentration of the acid increases. By increasing the concentration of hydrochloric acid from 0.0125M to 0.05M the diminution in the velocity at 488μ is found to be only about 12 per cent. Hence the concentration of hydrochloric acid (0.05M) used in these experiments is quite sufficient to prevent completely the disturbing influences due to the dissociation of hydrochloric acid and the hydrolysis of ferric chloride. For 448μ the difference observed is very small which is also to be expected. Even with 0.05M-hydrochloric acid absorption of the incident light is nearly complete at 448μ ; consequently when the concentration of hydrochloric acid is further reduced there is no material change in the amount of light absorbed and hence the velocity remains practically unaffected.

Hydrochloric acid has thus no effect on the velocity of this reaction except in so far as it diminishes the extinction coefficient for light of longer wave-lengths by ferric chloride solutions.

Influence of Temperature on the Velocity of Reactions.

The experiments were carried out at 25°, 33° and 43°. The temperature coefficient was always found to be unity.

*Influence of the Concentration of the Reacting Acids on the
Speed of Reaction.*

TABLE VII.

Reaction cell=1 cm. thick, 9 sq. cm. area.
Ferric chloride=0.025 M. Hydrochloric acid=0.05 N.

Conc. of the acid.	<i>x/t</i> in terms of N/500-thiosulphate for 2 c.c. of the reaction mixture.		
	488 $\mu\mu$. Energy = 2.22 \times 900 ergs.	448 $\mu\mu$. Energy ab- sorbed = 1.8 \times 900 ergs.	390 $\mu\mu$. Energy ab- sorbed = 0.838 \times 900 ergs.
<i>Mandelic acid.</i>			
0.5 M	3.1 c.c. *	2.57 c.c. *	1.2 c.c. *
0.2 M	2.98	2.45	—
0.1 M	2.8	2.33	1.06
0.05 M	2.5	2.15	0.92
0.025 M	2.1	1.9	0.75
<i>Lactic acid.</i>		Energy absorbed = 1.21 \times 900 ergs.	
0.5 M		0.76	
0.1 M		0.68	
0.05 M		0.59	
<i>Tartaric acid.</i>		Energy absorbed = 6.4 \times 900 ergs.	
0.5 M		4.0	
0.1 M		4.5	
0.05 M		4.6	
0.025 M		4.45	

It will be noticed that in the case of tartaric acid the influence of concentration of the acceptor molecule on the velocity of photo-reduction of ferric chloride is negligible, but in the case of lactic acid and mandelic acid, this influence is not inconsiderable. In fact, if the inverse of velocity of photo-reduction is plotted against the inverse of the concentration of the acceptor acid molecules, we get a straight line as will be evident from Fig. 1. Such dependence of the velocity constants on the concentration of acceptor molecules in the case of photochemical reactions has been observed in many cases in

this laboratory. Following Turner (*Phys. Review*, 1924, **23**, 464) it may be concluded that for a constant rate of production of excited ferric ion, the rate of reaction will be given by the equation,

$$V \text{ (velocity)} = C \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \quad \dots (1)$$

where τ is the life-period of the excited molecule, T is the interval on an average between successive collisions of an excited molecule and the acceptor molecule, and C is a constant.

$$T \text{ is further given by } \frac{1}{A\alpha^2 p}$$

where p is the osmotic pressure of ferric ion expressed in millimetres of mercury, α is the distance between the centres of the excited ferric ion and acceptor molecule on collision, and

$$A = 2666 \cdot 6 \sqrt{\frac{2\pi N}{K\theta} \cdot \frac{m + m_1}{m m_1}}$$

where $N = 6 \cdot 1 \times 10^{23}$, $K = 1 \cdot 371 \times 10^{16}$, θ = absolute temperature, m = molecular weight of ferric ion and m_1 = molecular weight of the organic acid.

$$\text{Equation (1) becomes } C \left[\frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{A\alpha^2 p \tau}} \right] = V$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{V} = \frac{1}{C} + \frac{1}{C} \cdot \frac{1}{A\alpha^2 \tau} \cdot \frac{1}{p} \quad \dots (2)$$

Hence $1/V$ plotted against $1/p$ should be a straight line which has been actually found to be the case.

Life-period of excited Ferric Ion.

Equation (2) enables us to calculate easily the life-period of an excited ferric ion. Assuming van't Hoff's equation, p the osmotic pressure in mm. of mercury can be easily calculated from the molar concentration of ferric salt. The slope of the curves is given by

$$\frac{1}{C} \cdot \frac{1}{A\alpha^2 \tau}$$

and the intercept on the $1/V$ axis for $1/p=0$ or $p=\infty$ is given by $1/C$.

$$\text{Therefore, } A\alpha^2\tau = \frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} \quad \text{or} \quad \tau = \frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} \cdot \frac{1}{A\alpha^2}.$$

Assuming $\alpha = 3 \times 10^{-8}$ cm., we obtain the values of τ given in Table VIII for excited states of ferric ion.

TABLE VIII.

Wave-length of exciting radiation.	Nature of acceptor molecules.	τ
488 $\mu\mu$	Mandelic acid	1.4×10^{-9}
448 $\mu\mu$	„	1.4×10^{-9}
390 $\mu\mu$	„	1.05×10^{-9}
448 $\mu\mu$	Lactic acid	1.1×10^{-9}

It will be noticed that the life periods are of the same order of magnitude ; α for collision between ferric ion and lactic acid and mandelic acid is taken to be identical. It is unmistakable that the higher the value of the quantum absorbed the smaller is the life-period of excitation.

In the case of tartaric acid, the reaction is complicated by the fact that the immediate product of photo-oxidation of tartaric acid is in a position to react with ferric salts under the influence of light. Here we are really dealing with a set of consecutive reactions which marks the peculiarities noted in the case of lactic acid and mandelic acid.

Photochemical Efficiency.

The reaction is characterised by great simplicity. The velocity constant is zero-molecular and is not affected by changes of temperature. Hence Einstein's law is expected to hold good. The following table gives the quantum efficiency of the reactions under various experimental conditions. A typical method of calculation is given below :—

Mandelic acid = 0.5M. Ferric chloride = 0.025 N.

Mean wave-length = 488 $\mu\mu$. Energy absorbed = 2.22×900 ergs.

The reaction cell is 1 cm. thick, and 9 sq. cm. area.

(*Vide* Table VII data marked with asterisk.)

The number of quanta absorbed =

$$\frac{2.22 \times 900 \times 488 \times 10^{-7} \times 9}{6.55 \times 10^{-27} \times 3 \times 10^{10}} = 4.4658 \times 10^{14}.$$

Total number of molecules transformed

$$= \frac{9 \times 3.1 \times 6.1 \times 10^{23}}{2 \times 1000 \times 500 \times 60 \times 60} = 4.7277 \times 10^{14}.$$

$$\frac{\text{No. of mols.}}{\text{No. of quanta}} = \frac{4.728 \times 10^{14}}{4.466 \times 10^{14}} = 1.06$$

Quantum Efficiency.

TABLE IX.

	488 $\mu\mu$.	448 $\mu\mu$.	390 $\mu\mu$.
Mandelic acid	1.06 mols.	1.18 mols.	1.36 mols.
Tartaric acid	0.49 ,,	0.52 ,,	0.8 ,,
Lactic acid	0.42 ,,	0.52 ,,	0.8 ,,

It will be seen from the above table that in the case of mandelic acid the quantum efficiency is 1 at 488 $\mu\mu$ but becomes nearly 1.4 at 390 $\mu\mu$. In the case of tartaric acid and lactic acid the number of molecules transformed per quantum of energy absorbed is nearly 0.5 at 488 $\mu\mu$ but goes on increasing as the frequency increases and becomes 0.8 at 390 $\mu\mu$.

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